

DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES AND SMALL INDUSTRY ZONES (THE EXAMPLE OF TERMIZ FREE ECONOMIC ZONE)

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Abstract.

The article shows the role and opportunities of the free economic zone and small industrial zones, especially the Termiz free economic zone, in the development of the country's economy and attracting foreign investments.

Keywords.

"Termiz" free economic zone (Termiz FEZ), special economic zone (SEZ), small industrial zone (SIZ), technology park, cluster, industrial enterprises, cooperation, competitive products, engineering-communication, logistics, financial services, production, road transport, social infrastructure, customs, tax, certification, transport, banking, currency exchange and mobile communication, medical and hotel services, car maintenance, etc.

Today, the role of international cooperation, including foreign investments, is of great importance in the development of the country's economy. We can clearly see that this can be achieved by expanding the activities of free economic zones and small industrial zones from the experience of developed countries in the world.

"If we can carefully formulate investment projects by regions and sectors for investors who want to invest in our economy, we can achieve a positive result on this issue. In this regard, it is necessary to regulate the placement of business entities in free economic zones and small industrial zones, as well as granting them privileges and preferences from an organizational and legal point of view."²⁷¹

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.

Further development of effective trade and transport-logistics relations with neighboring countries, especially the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, as well as ensuring the safety of international cargo transportation and expanding the transit potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan, comprehensive use of the resource base of

²⁷¹ D.Y.Xujamkulov. Free economic zones. Textbook. Tashkent-2019

the border regions and the right to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirzoyoyev dated September 18, 2018 No. PF-5540 on the establishment of the free economic zone "Termiz" in order to create favorable conditions for the active attraction of foreign direct investments "Termiz" free economic zone was established ²⁷²in Surkhandarya region.

The Termiz International Trade Center is being created on the basis of the Termiz Free Economic Zone, which has an infrastructure of storage, transportation and other modern services for manufacturers, exporters and buyers.

The free economic zone "Termiz" and the free trade zone "Termiz International Trade Center" are located on the territory of 120.6 hectares near the border of Surkhandarya region. Of this , the free economic zone "Termiz" - 54.6 hectares, the free trade zone "Termiz International Trade Center" - 66.0 hectares, of which the trade center - 26 hectares, the logistics center - 40 hectares.

It is 0.5 km from the border between Termiz - Islamic Republic of Afghanistan (Hairaton), and 105 km from Termiz - Mazari-Sharif.

Termiz - Torkham (Pakistan) is 800 km, Termiz - Karachi (Pakistan) is 1800 km.

Also, the region is connected with major cities of our country by means of transport and railway.

The following are the activities of "Termiz" FEZ main duties and directions reached marked:

- in the territory of the FEZ the first in line cluster approach wide used without SEZ participants between strong cooperation based on local raw material and materials basically competitive ready product and integral items work release localization according to high technology modern work releases set up reach;

- in FEZ areas industry enterprises and infrastructure in objects new qualified the work seats the creation of this based on republic regions of the population employment level and income increase provide;

- local mineral raw materials responses deep again work and to the world famous brands under high added valuable competitive products work release for own FEZ is established in the territories done of regions work release and resource from potential complex and efficient to use provide;

- work production , engineering-communication , road -transport and social infrastructure more development as well as quality logistics services show according to modern infrastructure formation;

²⁷² <https://lex.uz/> National database of legislative information of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Term of establishment of "Termiz" FEZ is 30 years, which can be extended later.

Special economic zones to the participants Uzbekistan Republic Tax code and Uzbekistan "Special economic zones about". In the law defined in order separately taxes and customs payments according to benefits of application to himself special features mean is caught and currency arrangements action does.

"Termiz" FEZ participants area to the limit external engineering communications and infrastructures construction equal to in shares Uzbekistan Republic of republic budget and Surkhandarya of the region local budget funds at the expense of done is increased.

The entire FEZ "Termiz" activity show during taxes and state purposeful to savings mandatory deductions from paying free will be done.

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 12, 2020, the Termiz international trade center is being established in the territory of the "Termiz" free economic zone.

"Surkhandarya" of our President province and in the city of Tashkent special economic and small industry zones activities more development measures about" decree acceptance was made (PF-6109, 12.11.2020).²⁷³

The total land area of the free trade zone "Termiz International Trade Center" is 26 hectares, the number of sales points - 260, the area of the parking lot - 3 hectares (capacity - 1000 cars), the number of hotels - 2 (400 seats).

During his visit to Surkhandarya region, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev inspected its master plan.

General the value was 75 million dollars this center huge and a lot network will be There are 1,800 sales point, for a cargo capacity of about 1 million tons have logistics center and warehouses, 1 thousand 600 square meters meter expo center as well as two hotel, hostel, hospital, car workshops and another objects set up is being done.

An area of 26 hectares has been allocated for the center in Termiz district, and construction work has started. On the first floor of the buildings, it is planned to place retail outlets, and on the second floor, light manufacturing enterprises.

International trade in the center special tax and customs mode, up to 10 days without a visa order, "single "window" principle based on service show to the road is placed. As a result work production and trade will develop. of the center yearly

²⁷³ <https://dunyo.info/> (<https://invest.gov.uz>)

trade turnover of 500 million dollars, export capacity of 200 million dollars intended. Here from a total of 5,600 more the work place creation can.

The borders of "Termiz" FEZ territories are determined, the programs for the development of the new zone, the order of import and export of goods, customs clearance, sale of products, as well as the entry, stay and exit of foreigners and vehicles in the country are approved.

One of the features of the Termiz ITC legal order is the provision of a number of basic services using interactive mechanisms based on the "one-stop shop" principle. These include customs, tax, certification, phytosanitary, veterinary, transport, banking, currency exchange and mobile communications, medical and hotel services, car maintenance and others.

In addition, Afghan citizens, as well as citizens of other countries and stateless persons entering from Afghanistan, may not receive entry visas (subject to personal and passport control) and may stay in the country for 10 days without temporary registration.

A working group on the development of the small industrial zone "Termiz" SEZ, Termiz ITC" was formed. The group is engaged in attracting potential investors, inter-agency coordination and development of external engineering, communication and transport infrastructure of these regions.

In order to finance Termiz and Sirgali Industrial Parks, the Ministry of Finance allocates 5 billion soums from the Government Reserve Fund to form statutory funds. The Recovery and Development Fund allocates loans in the amount of 20 million US dollars to the authorities of Surkhandarya region for the construction of necessary facilities.

The constructed and put into use objects are sold to the applicants through open auctions organized by the directorates of these zones or leased, and its order and price are determined by the working group. The proceeds will be used to repay loans.

Advantages of "Termiz" free economic zone and "Termiz International Trade Center" free trade zones:

- The market is a convenient location, access to the domestic market not only of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but also of Tajikistan, Afghanistan, Iran, and Pakistan.

- Logistics - one of the largest logistics centers in Central Asia operates in the free economic zone. Its area is 24 hectares. There are also 3.2 hectares of container space, 10.5 hectares of open space for temporary parking, 4 hangars with a total area of 6000 m².

- Financial services - High financial and banking services are organized for investors and buyers in the free economic zone.

- Skilled labor force - The population of the region is more than 2.7 million people. Higher educational institutions and vocational colleges train more than 30,000 highly qualified specialists every year.

- Communications - External roads, power lines, gas pipelines, water supply, etc. will be delivered to the free economic zone at the expense of state funds.

- Social infrastructure - There are modern hotels, entertainment centers, cafes and restaurants, grocery stores, etc. for investors and buyers in the territory of the free economic zone.

of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2021 "On measures to expand the territory of the Termiz free economic zone" was of great importance in defining the development prospects of the Termiz free economic zone.

According to the decree, in order to further expand the activities of the Termiz free economic zone, the territory of the free economic zone "Boysun-farm" was added to the territory of the Termiz FEZ. As of January 1, 2023, the number of special economic zones in Surkhandarya region reached 2, small industrial zones 25, technopark 1, clusters 44.

The total volume of production of industrial products by enterprises included in special economic zones, small industrial zones, technological parks and clusters is 62,716.8 billion. organized soum. From this: in SEZ - 27,252.1 bln. soums, in SIZ - 6,358.3 bln. soums, in the technopark - 427.2 billion. soums and in clusters - 28,679.2 bln. amounts to soum.

In 2022, the volume of investments in fixed capital by participating enterprises from all sources of financing is 7,622 bln. amounted to soums, of which: in SEZ - 3,735 bln. soums, in SIZ - 1,664 bln. soums, technopark - 156.4 billion. soums and in clusters - 2,066.5 bln. amounted to soum.

The information shows that the existing free economic zones and small industrial zones have a positive effect on the macroeconomic indicators of the country.

Summary. Based on the above, the following conclusions and suggestions can be made. The convenient geographical location of Termiz free economic zone, good infrastructure, proximity to Termiz international airport, logistics, service and trade center determine the development prospects of the region. In addition, the tax and other benefits given by our state to enterprises wishing to operate in the territory of

the free economic zone serve as a factor for not only local but also foreign investors to start their business without fear.

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